

Cure path sensitivity of snap-cure pre-pregs for layer-by-layer manufacturing

Robin Hartley, James Kratz

ICCM 23

Belfast, nth July 2022

Introduction

● Definitions:

● Purpose:

To characterise the reaction kinetics of our chosen snap cure material, and use this to develop a layer by layer manufacturing technique that is:

- Practical
- Industrially applicable

Cure path sensitive materials:

“Materials with mechanical/thermal properties that are sensitive to the cure path”

Snap cure material:

“A thermoset that cures an order of magnitude faster (second/minutes) than tradition thermosets (hours)”

Layer by layer manufacturing:

“A CFRP manufacturing method where deposition, consolidation and cure occur simultaneously in a layer by layer manner”

Motivation

● Three steps of composite processing:

- Fibre deposition
- Layer consolidation
- Matrix curing

Currently discrete. Why?

1. **History** – small parts and low production rates
2. **Technical challenge** – part quality

Motivation

● Why combine deposition, consolidation & cure?

- Need larger parts at faster rates
- Large parts = large autoclaves = \$\$\$

● How does layer-by-layer (LbL) combine them

- AFP style real time deposition/compaction head¹
- In-line heating unit to cure composite as it is deposited

● Benefits of layer-by-layer

- Thick part \neq exotherm
- Improved dimensional tolerances with thickness sensing¹
- No autoclave

Research Questions

- Material selection: Hexcel M78.1 42% UD300
 - Resin content
 - Carbon Fibre: Unidirectional, 300 gsm
 - Resin: Snap-cure epoxy @110 - 160 °C
- Snap-cure behaviour:
 - How does the material cure?
 - Is modelling the kinetics possible?
 - At what degree of cure does it gel?
- Cure path dependency:
 - Are any properties (e.g. T_g) affected by cure path?
 - How does this relate to microstructure?
- Layer-by-layer
 - How can the material behaviour be used to optimise the layer-by-layer process?

Cure Kinetics Modelling

- Dynamic DSC:
 - 2, 5, 10, 20 & 40 °C min⁻¹
 - Rapid heating in LbL
- Isothermal DSC:
 - 100-160 °C
 - Typical M78.1 cure temps
- Integrate heat flow

Cure Kinetics Modelling

M78.1 degree of cure and cure rate:

- 100 °C - 50 mins
- 110 °C - 30 mins
- 120 °C - 15 mins
- 130 °C - 6 mins
- 145 °C - 3 mins
- 160 °C < 3 mins

Cure Kinetics Modelling

Why is final degree of cure at 160 °C lower?

145 °C and 160 °C Iso excluded

Not very isothermal!

Cure Kinetics Modelling

Kamal Sourour model:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \frac{Ae^{-E_a/RT} \alpha^m (1 - \alpha)^n}{1 + e^{(D(\alpha - (\alpha_{C0} + \alpha_{CT}T)))}}$$

Diffusion control term²

Model fit to both the dynamic and isothermal degree of cure data

Cure Kinetics Validation

Heat transfer/curing experiment

- 20 plies thick
- Displacement control (20 × cpt)
- 5 °C min⁻¹ to 110 °C, 40 min hold

• 1D transient heat transfer

$$\rho c_p \frac{\delta T}{dt} = \frac{\delta}{\delta x} \left(k \frac{\delta T}{\delta x} \right) + q_v$$

Solve using finite difference method to get: $T(x, t)$

If cure kinetics are correct then internal heat generation should be accurate

Cure Kinetics Validation

Modelled vs measured T

Good agreement in both:

Isothermal phase

- Exotherm well represented :
 - Total heat of reaction accurate
 - Cure rate accurate

Dynamic phase

- No lag :
 - Thermal diffusivity accurate:

$$\kappa = \frac{k}{\rho c_p}$$

T_g and Reaction Onset

Quenched DSC isothermal experiments

- Cure isothermally (vary hold time)
- Quench reaction (drop temperature fast)
- Dynamic ramp to capture resulting T_g and α
- Fit data using DiBenedetto equation¹ (excluding 160 °C)

$$\frac{T_g - T_{g0}}{T_{g\infty} - T_{g0}} = \frac{\lambda\alpha}{1 - (1 - \lambda)\alpha}$$

Cure Path Dependency

Hypothesis:

“ T_g discrepancy caused by cure path dependency of microstructure”

How can this be proved?

Microstructure is locked in at gel. How does curing to gel at different temperatures followed by a post cure at either 130 °C or 160 °C affect the ultimate T_g ?

Experiment:

Stage 1

Partially cure isothermally up to α_{Gel} (0.41) at:

- 100 °C
- 130 °C
- 160 °C

Measure T_g

Stage 2

Cure to completion at:

- 130 °C
- 160 °C

Measure T_g

Cure Path Dependency

Results:

- Higher cure temperature up to gel generally results in higher ultimate T_g
- Higher stage 2 cure temperature results in lower ultimate T_g
- Potential causes:

- Inhomogeneous mixture of epoxy and hardener
- If entire cure is at 160 °C the two can't inter-diffuse before microstructure is locked in by network formation
- Results in under crosslinked regions which reduces the ultimate T_g

Stage	Cure temp. / °C	Cure time / s	T_g	Degree of cure
Stage 1	100	1243	44	0.35
	130	107	43	0.35
	160	25	41	0.33
Stage 2: 130 °C	130	600	110	0.84
	130	600	114	0.87
	130	600	130	0.96
Stage 2: 160 °C	160	600	105	0.81
	160	600	107	0.82
	160	600	115	0.87

Conclusions:

- Cure kinetics can be used to model M78.1 snap cure resin for single step cycles
- The ultimate T_g of the material is dependent on the cure temperature
- Higher temperatures result in rapid cure times but poorer thermal properties (cure path dependency)
- M78.1 is a suitable material system for the proposed layer-by-layer (LbL) manufacturing method
- Care must be taken when developing an M78.1/LbL process to avoid the property cure path dependency problems

robin.hartley@bristol.ac.uk

bristol.ac.uk/composites

Thank you to the:

Future Composites Manufacturing
Research Hub: EP/P006701/1